

DEFINITION AND HISTORY OF FINANCIAL TECHNOLOGIES

Etmishboev Shakhzodbek¹
Tolibjonov Khurshidbek²
Azamov Shoxruxmirzo³

¹Student of the Fergana branch of the TATU

²Student of Kokand University

³Student of the Fergana branch of the TATU

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6673007>

ARTICLE INFO

Received: 28th May 2022
Accepted: 02nd June 2022
Online: 05th June 2022

KEY WORDS

Fintech, startup, services, peer-to-peer, platform, market, bank

ABSTRACT

This article describes the history and origins of Financial Technology (Fintech). Attention is also paid to the application of financial technologies. The systems that have laid the foundation for its present place and its development in the past are filled with precise years and historical data. As you read this article, you will learn about the opinions of leading scholars in the field and what is happening in large companies.

The word Fintech (Financial technology) comes from a combination of two complementary industries: financial services and advanced technology-based solutions. The word "Fintech" entered the Oxford Dictionary as "computer software and other technologies used to support or enable banking and financial services". A business line based on the use of software to provide financial services. Fintech companies are typically established startups designed to disrupt existing financial systems and corporations that rely less on software. Fintech's simpler definition is an industry made up of organizations that use new financial technologies to support or enable financial services.

There are two main aspects that need to be considered - the main topic and the definition of coverage:

Fintech initiatives should not be seen as an ecosystem inhabited only by startups. The term is often associated with startups, as

the use of advanced digital solutions in financial services is a relatively modern trend. Even mature and large companies have begun to transform their businesses with advanced financial technology solutions, such as using online or mobile services.

Fintech initiatives cover a wide range of financial sectors. Lending Club, one of the largest peer-to-peer lending platforms in the world, directly connects borrowers and investors by making lending more convenient and making more profitable investments and promoting an entirely new lending program.

Kickstarter, a huge financing platform for creative projects, has drastically reduced the use of funds for startups or simple projects. Wealthfront combines finance and automation to manage assets through sophisticated algorithms. CommonBond is a market. a lender refinancing master's and undergraduate student loans. This reduced

the cost of student loans and saved an average of \$ 14,000 over the life of the loan. These examples illustrate the exact situation. Fintech companies are threatening traditional financial services. The former can offer more innovative and customer-oriented business models. These disruptive organizations are gradually gaining market share and revenue from traditional financial services, which are in dire need of a rethinking of business models and a change in strategy in order to be competitive in the market.

It's never been easier for Fintech startups. "Fintech is different from many other startups because the financial world is tightly regulated and consists mainly of a relatively small number of large, well-established companies," says Human Shadab, a law professor at New York Law School. He points to the challenges that the modern economic scenario poses to fintech initiatives.

Fintech is a relatively modern concept. It can be attributed to the first half of the XIX century, the introduction of the telegraph (1838) and later in 1866 the successful construction of the first transatlantic cable. Together these are two technological innovations. The late 1800s laid the groundwork for financial globalization. Nowadays, in the age of the internet of things, it can be hard to imagine a connected world where data flows with great difficulty across regions and continents. Before the successful completion of the transatlantic cable, communication between Europe and America was carried out only by ship. In addition to the duration of the voyages, there was a high risk of delays due to storms and shipwrecks. The importance and scope of this innovation is clear, even

for financial purposes. As an industry, banking was one of the first to adopt computers. The first basic computer for commercial use was built for banking. The banks themselves used computers to improve and speed up old processes that already existed.

What is recognized as one of the largest financial technologies of the last century is the ATM. In 2009, Paul Volker, former chairman of the U.S. Federal Reserve System, said, "The most important financial innovation I've seen in the last 20 years is a paid ATM that can really help people and prevent visits. ATM is a real convenience.

On June 27, 1967, Barclays Bank installed the first ATM in Enfield, United Kingdom. This has actually allowed people to commit financial robberies through electronic telecommunications devices. ATM is one of the first applications of technology in the financial sector, providing significant economic savings to financial institutions through the introduction of automation rather than human labor in the relationship between customers and financial institutions.

ATM innovation is interesting. This marked the beginning of a new fintech era. Since that day, the relationship between financial services and technology has waned. The ATM was the first innovation to clearly show the profound interdependence between finance and technology. The digitalization of the financial services sector was open. By the end of the 1980s, the industry remained, at least from a consumer perspective, largely based on analog technology.

The fintech industry, which marked 1987 as a turning point, points to two facts:

A stunning photo from Oliver Stone's Wall Street film depicts an investment banker using an early cell phone.

"Black Monday" stock market crash. One of the recognized reasons for the crash, which began in Hong Kong and immediately spread across Europe and the United States, was software trading: a computerized type of trading that involved the implementation of a basket of shares under predetermined conditions. In short, once prices reach certain limits, a computer app buys and sells shares.

Black brought the fact to the attention of regulators on Monday, highlighting the strong interrelationships and risks between financial and technology in the stock market crash. In particular, regulators have developed new rules and reviewed compensation protocols to introduce uniformity to the most current financial products. In order to control the rate of price changes, the New York Stock Exchange introduced automatic switches in addition to trading restrictions. In addition, efforts were made to develop cooperation. The 1990s saw the transition from analog to digital technologies for the financial services industry. The development of the World Wide Web and the first experiments of Internet banking marked the tenth anniversary of Well Fargo in the US and ING in Europe. In addition, the replacement of the telegraph first by fax and then by e-mail / instant messaging has strengthened

communication around the world and laid the foundation for strong financial relationships.

From the twenty-first century, the internal and external processes associated with the financial services industry have shifted to full digitalization. The importance of investment in the ICT sector shows that this sector is also relevant in the financial services industry.

Traditional financial institutions compete directly with fintech startups. The mobile phone has radically changed the way many customers choose banking services. In fact, in some parts of the world, it has allowed people to have a bank account. Fintech initiatives are spreading very fast, affecting new industries and affiliates. In 2009, Satoshi Nakamoto (pseudonym) introduced a new type of currency called Bitcoin (Skinner 2016). It is a form of digital currency for transactions without the involvement of central banks or other intermediaries.

In short, as time goes on, new technologies will take over and rule the world. The future is more uncertain than ever. The level of innovation in the financial sector is very high. The reactions of traditional financial institutions do not have to be successful. Considering the opinion of experts, scientists and practitioners, fintech initiatives will continue to grow in the future.

References:

1. Agrawal, A. K., Catalini, C., & Goldfarb, A. (2014). Some simple economics of crowdfunding. *Innovation Policy and the Economy*.
2. Al-Fedaghi, S. S., & Taha, M. M. (2006). Personal information eWallet. *IEEE International Conference on Systems, Man, Cybernetics*,
3. Arner, D. W., Barberis, J., & Buckley, R. P. (2015). The evolution of FinTech.
4. <https://www.economiafinanzas.com/uz/fintech-que-es/>